

A model for the number of variants that are homozygous for the alternative allele

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In this document, I derive the following expression for the number of variants that are homozygous for the alternative allele in the autosomal exome of Homo sapiens:

$$N_{hom} = \frac{N_c}{4} \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha + \beta} F \left(1, \alpha + 1; \alpha + \beta + 1; \frac{1}{2} \right) + \frac{\gamma}{\gamma + \delta} F \left(1, \gamma + 1; \gamma + \delta + 1; \frac{1}{2} \right) \right)$$

where F is the hypergeometric series (see Eq. 6) and N_c is the total number of variants in the autosomal exome. This formula is based on the assumption that the distribution of the frequency of the alternative alleles in the autosomal subset of the exome of Homo sapiens is given by

$$f(p) = \sigma \frac{p^{\alpha-1}(1-p)^{\beta-1}}{B(\alpha, \beta)} + (1-\sigma) \frac{p^{\gamma-1}(1-p)^{\delta-1}}{B(\gamma, \delta)}, \quad \begin{cases} \alpha, \beta < 1 \\ \gamma, \delta > 1 \\ 0 < \sigma < 1 \end{cases}$$

These formulae are applied to an actual exome and the theoretical computation of N_{hom} is compared with the corresponding experimental number.

Let N_c be the total number of calls of the average VCF file from WES. It can also be the number of calls in a subset of chromosomes, like for instance in the autosomal ones. If we indicate with p the frequency of the alternative allele, we can assume that there is a density $f(p)$ such that the number of positions across the genetic region considered in which the alternative allele has frequency included in $[p, p + \Delta p]$ is given by

$$\text{Eq. 1} \quad \Delta N_c = N_c \int_p^{p+\Delta p} f(p) dp \Leftrightarrow dN_c(p) = N_c f(p) dp$$

The histogram of the frequency of the alternative alleles in the exonic regions of the autosomal chromosomes of my exome is reported in Figure 1. If we consider the possible shapes that the beta distribution can assume (Figure 2), one possible way to reproduce this density is to make the position

$$\text{Eq. 2} \quad f(p) = \sigma \frac{p^{\alpha-1}(1-p)^{\beta-1}}{B(\alpha, \beta)} + (1-\sigma) \frac{p^{\gamma-1}(1-p)^{\delta-1}}{B(\gamma, \delta)}, \quad \begin{cases} \alpha, \beta < 1 \\ \gamma, \delta > 1 \\ 0 < \sigma < 1 \end{cases}$$

A plot of this density (it is a density because its integral on \mathbb{R} is one) is reported in Figure 3. If we are interested in the number of positions in which the subject is homozygous for the alternative allele, we can consider that

$$dN_{hom} = P(hom|call) dN_c = \frac{P(hom \cap call)}{P(call)} dN_c = \frac{P(hom)}{P(hom) + P(het)} dN_c$$

where we have considered that $P(hom \cap call) = P(hom)$ and that $P(call) = P(hom) + P(het)$. But $P(hom) = p^2$ and $P(het) = 2p(1-p)$. Therefore, we have

$$dN_{hom} = \frac{p^2}{p^2 + 2p(1-p)} dN_c = \frac{p^2}{2p - p^2} dN_c = \frac{p}{2-p} dN_c$$

Integration with respect to p leads to the conclusion that:

$$\text{Eq. 3} \quad N_{hom} = N_c \int_0^1 \frac{pf(p)}{2-p} dp = \frac{N_c}{2} \int_0^1 \frac{pf_1(p)}{2-p} dp + \frac{N_c}{2} \int_0^1 \frac{pf_2(p)}{2-p} dp$$

Figure 1. The density of the frequency of the alternative allele on the autosomal chromosomes of my WES.

Figure 2. The beta distribution for different values of the parameters. Note that the blue curve requires that $a < b < 1$. If we have $b < a < 1$, the shape is the specular one with respect to the axis $x = 0.5$. From (1), without permission.

Figure 3. The plot of the function in Eq. 2 for $a = 0.2, b = 0.5, c = 2$. In this case we have written a instead of α , and so forth.

Where we make the positions

$$\text{Eq. 4} \quad f_1(p) = \frac{p^{\alpha-1}(1-p)^{\beta-1}}{B(\alpha,\beta)}, \quad f_2(p) = \frac{p^{\gamma-1}(1-p)^{\delta-1}}{B(\gamma,\delta)}$$

Note now that

$$\int_0^1 \frac{p f_1(p)}{2-p} dp = \int_0^1 \frac{p}{2-p} \frac{p^{\alpha-1}(1-p)^{\beta-1}}{B(\alpha,\beta)} dp = \frac{1}{B(\alpha,\beta)} \int_0^1 \frac{p^\alpha(1-p)^{\beta-1}}{2-p} dp$$

The integral is known: it is equation 3.197.3 of (2) that with the present symbology gives

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^1 \frac{p^\alpha(1-p)^{\beta-1}}{2-p} dp &= \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 p^{(\alpha+1)-1} (1-p)^{\beta-1} \left(1 - \frac{p}{2}\right)^{-1} dp = \\ &= \frac{1}{2} B(\alpha+1, \beta) F\left(1, \alpha+1; \alpha+\beta+1; \frac{1}{2}\right) = \frac{\alpha}{2(\alpha+\beta)} B(\alpha, \beta) F\left(1, \alpha+1; \alpha+\beta+1; \frac{1}{2}\right) \Rightarrow \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Eq. 5} \quad \int_0^1 \frac{p f_1(p)}{2-p} dp = \frac{\alpha}{2(\alpha+\beta)} F\left(1, \alpha+1; \alpha+\beta+1; \frac{1}{2}\right)$$

with the request that $\alpha+1, \beta > 0$. The function F is the Gauss hypergeometric function and it is defined as follows

$$\text{Eq. 6} \quad F(a, b; c; x) = 1 + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{a(a+1)\dots(a+k)b(b+1)\dots(b+k)}{c(c+1)\dots(c+k)(k+1)!} x^{(k+1)}$$

which can be written also

$$F(a, b; c; x) = 1 + \frac{ab}{c} x + \frac{a(a+1)b(b+1)}{c(c+1)2!} x^2 + \frac{a(a+1)(a+2)b(b+1)(b+2)}{c(c+1)(c+2)3!} x^3 + \dots$$

We can also immediately derive the integral

$$\text{Eq. 7} \quad \int_0^1 \frac{pf_2(p)}{2-p} dp = \frac{\gamma}{2(\gamma+\delta)} F\left(1, \gamma+1; \gamma+\delta+1; \frac{1}{2}\right)$$

Therefore, we can write Eq. 3 as follows

$$\text{Eq. 8} \quad N_{hom} = \frac{N_c}{2} \left(\frac{\alpha\sigma}{\alpha+\beta} F\left(1, \alpha+1; \alpha+\beta+1; \frac{1}{2}\right) + \frac{\gamma(1-\sigma)}{\gamma+\delta} F\left(1, \gamma+1; \gamma+\delta+1; \frac{1}{2}\right) \right)$$

We must now find $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta$ in order to calculate N_{hom}, N_{het} . Note that the cumulative distribution function of $f(p)$ is

$$\begin{aligned} F_{CDF}(p) &= \left(\frac{\sigma}{B(\alpha, \beta)} \int_0^p x^{\alpha-1} (1-x)^{\beta-1} dx + \frac{1-\sigma}{B(\gamma, \delta)} \int_0^p x^{\gamma-1} (1-x)^{\delta-1} dx \right) = \\ &= \sigma \frac{B_p(\alpha, \beta)}{B(\alpha, \beta)} + (1-\sigma) \frac{B_p(\gamma, \delta)}{B(\gamma, \delta)} \end{aligned}$$

where B_p is the value of the incomplete beta function in p . If we now define a partition p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n of $[0,1]$, we can run a linear regression between the values $F_{CDF}(p_i)$ and the corresponding values of the experimental cumulative distribution function. I found the idea of this approach to regression in a paper of experimental geology (3). We can run these regressions for many possible combinations of the four parameters $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta$ and then pick the combination that reaches the highest R^2 . This task is performed by the R script at the end of this document and the best fit is the one in Figure 4, with $\alpha = 0.75, \beta = 0.80, \gamma = 0.90, \delta = 2.4, \sigma = 0.7$.

Figure 4. Plot of the function in Eq. 2 for $\alpha = 0.75, \beta = 0.80, \gamma = 0.90, \delta = 2.4, \sigma = 0.7$. In this case we have written a instead of α , and so forth.

If we now calculate the number of homozygous calls according to Eq. 3 with this set of parameters, we have

$$\text{Eq. 9} \quad N_{hom} = 39,853$$

while the direct count of homozygous calls is 45,714. The R code used to generate Figure 3 and Figure 4 to calculate Eq. 3 is the following one. Note that you need to install the package hypergeo to calculate the hypergeometric functions.

```
# file name: homozygosity_fit3
#
# Rome, December 21st 2023
#
#-----
# We read a file with the G1000 frequencies for the alternative allele in the
# first column and the homozygosity status (hom or het) in the second one. It
# can come from any subset of DNA (autosomal exome, autosomal genome, etc).
# Values are separated by semicolon.
#-----
#
library(hypergeo)
mydata<-read.csv("pam_exome_auto_G1000.csv", sep=";",header=T) # AF and status for each call
#
# We calculate the percentage of homozygous calls
#
l_tot<-length(mydata[,1])
l_hom<-0
for (i in 1:l_tot) {
  if (mydata[i,2]=="hom") l_hom<-l_hom+1
}
homozygosity<-l_hom/l_tot
#
# We set as zero the values of the frequencies without content
#
for (i in 1:l_tot) {
  if (mydata[i,1]== "." | mydata[i,1]== "" | mydata[i,1]== " ") mydata[i,1]<-0
}
#
# We coerce the frequencies as numbers
#
mydata$X1000G_<-as.numeric(mydata$X1000G_)
#
#-----
# Perform linear regression between the experimental cumulative distribution function
# and the analytic CDF for several combinations of the parameters alpha, beta, gamma
#-----
#
AF<-seq(from=0,to=1,by=1/100) # array of alternative allele frequency
X<-ecdf(mydata$X1000G_) # experimental cumulative distribution function
#
alpha<-seq(from=0.0001,to=1,by=1/20) # array for alpha
beta<-alpha # array for beta
gamma<-seq(from=1.0001,to=3,by=0.1) # array for gamma
delta<-gamma # array for delta
sigma<-c(0.1,0.3,0.5,0.7,0.9) # array for sigma
len<-length(alpha)*(length(beta)-1)*length(gamma)*length(delta)*length(sigma)*0.5 # number of trials
results<-data.frame(sigma=rep(NA,len),alpha=rep(NA,len),beta=rep(NA,len),gamma=rep(NA,len),
  delta=rep(NA,len),R2=rep(NA,len))
#
len<-length(alpha)
Y<-c()
```

```

q<-1
for (i in 1:(len-1)) { # set a value for alpha
  for (j in (i+1):len) { # set a value for beta
    for (k in 1:length(gamma)) { # set a value for gamma
      for (h in 1:length(delta)) { # set a value for delta
        for (l in 1:length(sigma)) { # set a value for sigma
          for (m in 1:length(AF)) Y[m]<-sigma[l]*pbeta(AF[m],alpha[i],beta[j])+
            (1-sigma[l])*pbeta(AF[m],gamma[k],delta[h])
          reg<-lm(Y~X(AF))
          results$sigma[q]<-sigma[l]
          results$alpha[q]<-alpha[i]
          results$beta[q]<-beta[j]
          results$gamma[q]<-gamma[k]
          results$delta[q]<-delta[h]
          results$R2[q]<-summary(reg)$r.squared
          q<-q+1
        }
      }
    }
  }
}
#
#-----
# Plot the best fit
#-----
#
# parameters of the best fit
#
max_row<-which.max(results$R2)
s<-results$sigma[max_row]
a<-results$alpha[max_row]
b<-results$beta[max_row]
c<-results$gamma[max_row]
d<-results$delta[max_row]
for (h in 1:length(AF)) Y[h]<-s*pbeta(AF[h],a,b)+(1-s)*pbeta(AF[h],c,d)
reg<-lm(Y~X(AF))
#
# plot of the regression line
#
plot(Y~X(AF),xlab="experimental",ylab="analytic",col="red",pch=20,cex=1)
abline(coef=reg$coefficients,lwd=2,col="black")
#
# We create an histogram for the frequency of the alternative allele
#
m<-mean(mydata$X1000G_,na.rm=T)
V<-var(mydata$X1000G_,na.rm=T)
hist(mydata$X1000G_,breaks=100,freq=F,col="lightblue",
      xlim=c(0,1),xlab="Frequency of the alternative allele", ylab="density of SNVs",ylim=c(0,2.5))
abline(v=m)
#
# We overlap to the theoretical distribution
#
par(new=T)
xvals<-seq(0,1,length=300)
f1<-dbeta(xvals,a,b)
f2<-dbeta(xvals,c,d)
plot(xvals,f1,type="l",col="black",lty=2,lwd=2,ylim=c(0,2.5),xlab="",ylab="")

```

```

par(new=T)
plot(xvals,f2,type="l",col="black",lty=3,lwd=2,ylim=c(0,2.5),xlab="",ylab="")
par(new=T)
plot(xvals,s*f1+(1-s)*f2,type="l",col="red",lty=1,lwd=2,ylim=c(0,2.5),xlab="",ylab="")
str<-expression(paste("f=","sigma","f1+", "(1-", "sigma,")f2"))
legend("top",legend=c("f1=Beta(a,b)", "f2=Beta(c,d)",str),lty=c(2,3,1),col=c(rep("black",3)))
#
# We calculate the theoretical number of homozygous calls
#
Nc<-l_tot # number of variants in the autosomal exome
#
temp1<-(a/(a+b))*hypergeo(1,a+1,a+b+1,0.5)
temp2<-(c/(c+d))*hypergeo(1,c+1,c+d+1,0.5)
n_hom<-(Nc/2)*(s*temp1+(1-s)*temp2)

```

References

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